

The Mechanistic Paradigm on International Education

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The influence of the mechanistic paradigm on international education is reflected in the idea that ethnic or multicultural studies boil down to the study of exotic or minority cultures. The dominant culture is rarely included on the same level as others, and the notion that minority or dependent cultures may influence it receives little or no consideration. We speak of Portuguese influence in Africa and Asia more often than we talk about the way this conviviality has transformed our culture. Similar parallels could be established for language relations between peoples.

It is becoming increasingly difficult for men and women today to conceive of all aspects of reality in which they are inserted according to the dictates of the mechanistic paradigm. The easy access to information and the effort to democratize education has given rise to a population that is better able to understand what suits them. It is increasingly aware of their right to participate in decisions that affect their lives.

The pressures exerted by increasingly distinct societies in its multicultural and multi-linguistic ways calls for a truly international school.

The worldwide commerce, industry, and public service require the formation of young people capable of a continually evolving world.

It is not enough to train students in the specific skills of different professions, as the ongoing technological revolution reduces to obsolete what was new yesterday.

On the other hand, both the factory and the office undergo major changes. An increasingly well-prepared workforce no longer tolerates the inhumanity of the traditional assembly line, nor working conditions that separate manual activity from its spiritual and psychic complements.

The company's need for power and instant decision making at all levels makes it impractical

The rigid hierarchy system that has hitherto worked. Taylor and Weber can no longer explain this new manifestation of human relations. The world is beginning to be perceived as a complex reality, composed of intertwined and increasingly interdependent elements, in short, as a series of systems.

Systems theory had its origin in the biological sciences, and it was biologists, such as Ludwig von Bertalanffy, who first proposed it. When comparing the life of physical organisms with the experience of a social aggregate, it is impossible not to find similarities and to establish parallels in terms of structures and functions.

The interdependence and interconnection of all people are hard to ignore.

The simplest organisms, whether biological or social, each element depends on one another in an unbroken chain of interaction.

Interaction, in turn, causes the influence of one organism on another to set in motion a process of change that affects all the organs of that system.

Change in an order is not; however, the cumulative result of all changes undergone by its elements. The transformed system is, in many ways, a new and more extensive network. The whole is thus more significant than the sum of its parts.

The transformed system will, in turn, influence other policies in an endless cycle.

This transformative interaction cannot occur randomly. The systems have homeostatic mechanisms capable of maintaining not only balance but also regulating the intensity and pace of the change process. This balance, however, is dynamic and tends to promote system development, never to hinder or contain it.

In one system, the relations between the various elements cannot, in turn, be based on the concept of power as imposing power, but must be influenced by another manifestation of power - the cooperative power.

In this context, the more distributed the power, the stronger its influence.

Power increases the force with which a small number over the majority imposes it. Development is achieved through the distribution of power among the different components of the system.

It is allowing them an interactive autonomy that results in the expansion of their creative capacities and the expansion of their human potential.

Cooperative power thus lies not in the intensity with which it is exercised, but in the way in which it strengthens and develops the whole system.

The notion of cooperative power is also not in line with the concept of linear causality. Human existence is too complex to be explained by such over-simplifications of this concept. Generally, simplifications of this nature tend to complicate everything. A simple observation of the world and its functioning leads us to a more coherent and convincing understanding of functions and the quality of its interactions.

System theories have inspired thinkers to try to explain the world by other paradigms.

Harvard's Richard Katz and Joanna Macy have, in recent years, outlined the infrastructure of a new paradigm, which they have called synergistic.

This model is based on a perception of reality as an interactive, intertwined, and dynamic whole. In the mechanical model, the notion of objectivity is defined and based on the separation between observers and observed.

In the synergistic model, observer and observed are intertwined, and the old notion of objectivity and knowledge is inexistent.

This new, distinct, but no less revolutionary way of perceiving reality has been preceded and influenced by scientific investigations, especially in biology (DNA), physics (quantum theories), and even engineering with neuro systems.

In the synergistic model, international education implies the analysis of different cultures on the same plane, and all their interweaving and their dynamics.

In an international school, designed to promote human and social development, based on the principles of respect for all cultures and the reciprocity of their influences, organizational structures must foster the interaction of all their elements - students, teachers, and administrators - to achieve the agreed objectives.

Respect for other cultures, however, means affirming the culture of each student and each teacher. It avoids the risk dehumanizing cultural invasion. Throughout this process, the expression of the primacy of the concept of education over the idea of instruction should be kept alive. Interestingly, students come to the knowledge of different realities, not to receive the version of a knowledge transmitted in second or third hands.

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